

FRACTURE MACHANICS OF CONCRETE REINFORCED WITH HEMP, STRAW AND ELEPHANT GRASS FIBRES

I. Merta^{1*}, E. K. Tschegg¹, S. E. Stanzl-Tschegg², A. Kolbitsch¹

¹ University of Technology Vienna, Austria, ² University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria

* Corresponding author (ildiko.merta@tuwien.ac.at)

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1 General Introduction

Concrete is one of the most widely used building material in civil engineering. However, as a very brittle material it has low tension strength and fracture energy. As a result, cracks develop whenever loads give rise to tensile stresses exceeding the tensile strength of concrete. The addition of different fibres to concrete matrix substantially enhances the energy absorption capacity of the plane concrete [1, 2, 3]. Consideration of the fracture energy is important since it determines the ductility and crack resistance of the structure assuring the safety and integrity of the structural element prior to its complete failure. [4]. Concrete is typically reinforced with steel or synthetic fibres like carbon, glass, or aramid. Despite of their advantages the high material costs, the high energy-consuming process by the production, and their adverse environmental impact has initiated the search of new environmental friendly and sustainable alternatives. A considerable research effort is going on in the exploitation of fast growing, annually renewable, cheap agricultural crops and crop residues as possible fibre reinforcement in concrete. The basic advantage of natural fibres is that they are a low cost and widely available resource in many agricultural areas.

In order to investigate the influence of natural fibres on the energy absorption capacity of concrete, in this research an experimental study of the fracture energy of concrete reinforced with natural fibres of hemp, elephant grass, and straw has been carried out. The uniaxial fracture energy of concrete specimens containing 0,19% of fibres by weight and of 40mm of length has been tested with the wedge splitting test (WST) method according to Tschegg [5, 6]. The fibres were used as they come from

nature without any kind of preparation ensuring in such a way a low cost building material.

2 Experimental Program

2.1 Concrete Specimens

Concrete specimens were fabricated with maximal aggregate size of 16mm and water to cement ratio, w/c of 0.67. Chopped fibres of hemp, wheat straw, and elephant grass of 40mm of length were added to the concrete matrix as fibre reinforcement (Figure 1). The measured tensile strength of the fibres is as follows: 600 N/mm² for hemp; 40 N/mm² for straw, and 60 N/mm² for elephant grass. The fibres content was 4.5 kg/m³ which results in a fibre percentage in the reinforced concrete of 0.19% by weight. For each type of the fibres a series of five cubic specimens of dimensions 150x150x130mm were produced.

2.2 The Wedge Splitting Test Method

In the research the fracture properties of the concrete specimens have been determined with the widely adopted wedge splitting test method (WST), originally developed by Tschegg [5, 6]. It is a very stable fracture mechanics test capable to determine accurately the load displacement diagram of the test specimens beyond the maximum load [7]. The major advantages of the WST are that the specimens are small and compact, the method does not require any sophisticated test equipment; it stores little elastic energy during testing and is well suited for inverse analysis. The WST method was comprehensively investigated by many scientists and it has been proved reliable for fracture testing of ordinary concrete at early age and later for lightweight concrete and for concrete reinforced with steel and

synthetic fibres [8, 9, 10, 11]. Figure 1 shows the fundamental structure of the WST method for uniaxial loading of a cubic specimen. A starter notch is cut into the rectangular groove of the specimen (Figure 2a). The load transmission pieces are inserted into this groove (Figure 2b) in which the slender wedge is laid. The force F_M from the testing machine is transmitted via the load transmission pieces onto the wedge, leading to splitting of the specimen. The friction between wedge and force transmission pieces is negligible and the splitting force F_H can be determined by means of a simple calculation. The vertical force F_V is low and does not disturb the fracture behaviour. The crack mouth opening displacement (CMOD) is determined at the height of the load application line on both sides by electronic displacement transducers. The two electronic displacement transducers are used on the one hand to obtain the average of the load displacement and on the other hand serve as crack behaviour detectors. If the crack runs obliquely to the notch, the specimen is eliminated.

From the CMOD the fracture energy absorbed by the specimens during the crack propagation has been calculated. All tests were carried out at an average ambient temperature of 22°C and an average relative humidity of 50%. The loading process was controlled by the notch opening at the rate of 5mm/min.

3 Results

3.1 Specimen's Tensile Strength

The mean value and the standard deviation of the splitting tensile strength of the specimens are given in the Figure 3. The mean value of the splitting tensile strength was up to 4%, 7%, and 8% lower for hemp, straw, and elephant grass reinforced specimens, respectively, compared to unreinforced concrete specimens. As expected the presence of the fibres does not have much influence on the tensile strength of the concrete.

3.2 Specimen's Fracture Energy

The fracture energy G_f [N/m] is defined as the post-crack energy absorption ability of fibre reinforced material and it represents the fracture energy that the structure will absorb during failure. The fracture energy of the specimens was calculated as the area

under the splitting force-displacement curve up to a defined displacement of 1.5 mm divided by the area of the fracture plane. The mean values and standard deviation of the fracture energy for each series of the test specimens is given in Figure 4.

A typical load-displacement curve of a concrete specimen without fibres and specimens reinforced with hemp, elephant grass, and straw is presented in Figure 5. The results shows that the presence of the fibres in concrete enhances the fracture energy of the plane concrete. The most distinctive increase in fracture energy of fibre reinforced specimens compared to unreinforced concrete specimens was observed by hemp fibre specimens, i.e., up to 70%. Reinforcement with straw and elephant grass fibres resulted in minimal enhancement of the fracture energy of the concrete, 2% and 5%, respectively (Figure 4).

The significant enhancement of fracture energy of the concrete when reinforced with hemp fibres is believed to be a result of the extreme fineness of the fibres, ensuring in such a way a good adhesion and friction to the concrete matrix. As a consequence the fibres extremely high tension strength could have been utilised in greater extend enhancing the fracture energy of the specimens extremely.

By straw and elephant grass fibres pure bond was observed with the concrete matrix, and as a consequence, failure appeared to be associated primarily with fibre pull-out. Enhancing the surface roughness of the fibres could result in a better adhesion and friction with concrete, resulting in higher energy dissipation through the fibres rupture.

4. Conclusion

Reinforcing concrete with natural fibres could provide an environmental friendly and low cost building material. Natural fibres are a low cost and widely available resource in many agricultural areas. Their use as reinforcement in concrete is a way to recycle the fibres and to produce a high performance material.

The results of this research demonstrated that if hemp fibers are added as reinforcement to concrete the fracture energy was increased up to 70%, obtaining in such a way a very promising composite material. However, the employment of straw and elephant grass fibres as concrete reinforcement is believed to be rather limited.

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Fig. 1. Chopped fibres of hemp, straw, and elephant grass

Fig. 3. Tensile strength of the specimens

Fig. 4. Fracture energy of the specimens

Fig.2. a) Specimens shape and b) Principle of the wedge splitting test according to Tschegg

Fig. 5. Force- displacement curve of the specimens

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